

Cellulose nanocrystals as a tunable nanomaterial for pervaporation membranes with asymmetric transport properties

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ABSTRACT

The cost-effective recovery of alcohols from aqueous fermentation broths is crucial in the production of biofuels. In this context, pervaporation processes using dense membranes have attracted remarkable interest. Cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) have emerged as a promising renewable component for membrane applications due to their high specific surface area and tunable surface chemistry. We recently reported compositionally graded nanocomposite membranes based on a hydrophobic poly(styrene)-*block*-poly(butadiene)-*block*-poly(styrene) (SBS) matrix and CNCs that display directional water transport properties. We here explore the ethanol-recovery pervaporation performance of such graded membranes for a model ethanol-water mixture. We further decorated the CNCs with hydrophobic oleic acid moieties (OLA-CNCs) and studied the impact of this modification on the structure and pervaporation performance of SBS/OLA-CNC nanocomposite membranes. Depending on the exposure side, SBS/CNC membranes exhibit either improved or diminished mass fluxes compared to the reference SBS membranes, but also a consistent reduction of the membrane selectivity towards ethanol. By contrast, the SBS/OLA-CNC membranes display increased ethanol permeability while their separation performance is comparable to the reference SBS membranes. Thus, we show that by tuning the surface chemistry of CNCs, the pervaporation properties and the degree of asymmetry in mass transport can be tailored.

1. Introduction

It is projected that worldwide oil demands will have increased by 16% in 2040 reaching a value of 111×10^6 barrels per day [1]. Driven by the increased oil demands and sustainability concerns, liquid biofuels have emerged as renewable alternatives to petroleum-based products [2]. In this context, alcohol-based fuels, such as bioethanol and biobutanol, have already partially replaced petrochemically derived liquid fuels with an expected annual bioethanol production of 1.4×10^{11} L by 2026 [3]. These biofuels are essentially the desirable products of biomass fermentation processes. However, sustainable separation methods are required to effectively isolate the alcohols from the aqueous fermentation broths [4–6].

Among these separation methods, pervaporation has received remarkable interest as an environmentally friendly option with several advantages such as the possibility for a continuous process, the avoidance of auxiliary solvents, and presumably lower energy demands than other methods such as distillation [5,7–10]. In pervaporation systems, a liquid feed stream, such as a fermentation broth, is circulated over a molecularly porous (i.e., dense) membrane. Vacuum is usually applied

on the opposite side of the membrane, thus creating a concentration gradient for the permeating species to diffuse through the mass transfer barrier. Depending on the affinity of the penetrants to the membrane, mass transport is favored or hindered resulting in the separation of the permeating species.

For the case of ethanol recovery with pervaporation from ethanol-water mixtures, a hydrophobic ethanol-selective membrane is required to enrich the permeate with ethanol [11]. A common strategy to improve the pervaporation performance is to employ mixed-matrix membranes, which can increase the tortuosity of the diffusion pathways and/or regulate the solubility of the penetrants in the membrane [11–15]. Dense nanocomposite membranes, prepared by incorporating at least one nanofiller into a polymer matrix, have attracted remarkable scientific interest for several membrane separation methods — including pervaporation — primarily due to the increased interfacial filler-matrix interactions and the interference with the macromolecular packing of the matrices [12,14–17]. Interestingly, nanocellulose — an emerging renewable nanomaterial that is isolated primarily from plants, which produce cellulose, the most abundant biopolymer on earth — still lacks notable scientific attention in the context of pervaporation processes [18–22], despite the extensive progress in other membrane/barrier

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Nomenclature	
A	Permeation area (m^2)
BS	Bottom side of cast membranes (facing the mold)
$C.I.$	Crystallinity index (–)
CNCs	Cellulose nanocrystals
DS_{bulk}	Bulk degree of substitution of cellulose nanocrystals
DS_s	Surface degree of substitution of cellulose nanocrystals
EtOH	Ethanol
H_2O	Water
J	Mass flux (g h^{-1})
\hat{j}	Area-normalized mass flux ($\text{g h}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$)
ℓ	Thickness (μm)
M_0	Dry weight of membrane (g)
M_∞	Equilibrium weight of membrane after solvent swelling (g)
m	Weight fraction of penetrant (wt %)
NPR	Thickness normalized permeation rate ($\text{kg } \mu\text{m h}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$)
OLA	Oleic acid
OLA-CNCs	Oleic acid-modified cellulose nanocrystals
P	Permeability ($\text{kg m m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1} \text{Pa}^{-1}$)
PAF	Permeability Asymmetry Factor (–)
PSI	Pervaporation Separation Index ($\text{g h}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$)
P	Partial vapor pressure (Pa)
R_c	Ratio of available particle surface chains (%)
RCN	Relative concentration of nanocellulose (–)
SBS	Poly(styrene)- <i>block</i> -poly(butadiene)- <i>block</i> -poly(styrene)
SSub%	Percentage of surface substitution (%)
T	Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)
THF	Tetrahydrofuran
TsCl	<i>p</i> -Toluenesulfonyl chloride
US	Upper side of cast membranes (facing the air)
x	Mole fraction of penetrant (mol %)
<i>Greek letters</i>	
α	Membrane selectivity (–)
β	Separation factor (–)
γ	Activity coefficient (–)
λ	Wavelength (nm)
θ	Scattering angle ($^\circ$)
<i>Superscripts and Subscripts</i>	
BS US	Permeation from the bottom side towards the upper side of the membrane
e	Ethanol
ew	Ethanol – water ratio
i	Penetrant
r	Retentate side
L	Liquid feed
l	Permeate side
sat	Saturated conditions
w	Water
US BS	Permeation from the upper side towards the bottom side of the membrane

applications such as filtration processes [23–27] and packaging applications [28–30]. Among the different types of nanocellulose, cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) have been in the spotlight as a primary or secondary membrane component [31]. Research on CNCs for membrane applications is driven mainly by the increased specific surface area of CNCs compared to other types of nanocellulose [27], their amendable surface chemistry [32], their outstanding reinforcing potential [33], the renewable nature of cellulose [28,30], as well as the lower potential toxicity in comparison to other nanomaterials such as carbon nanotubes [31,34,35].

CNCs are highly crystalline rod-like nanoparticles that can be isolated by carefully tuned acid hydrolysis processes of cellulosic sources which selectively remove their dislocated regions [36]. These nanoparticles have been employed in some pervaporation studies [21,22,37,38], although — to the best of our knowledge — never in the context of ethanol recovery from water, perhaps due to the *a priori* thermodynamic incompatibility between the utilized hydrophobic membrane matrices and the relatively polar surface chemistry of CNCs [39,40]. To tackle this incompatibility issue, modification strategies of CNCs with non-polar moieties in a covalent or non-covalent manner are routinely used to allow their homogeneous incorporation in non-polar polymers [32,39,40]. Moreover, CNCs are highly crystalline, and can inhibit the permeation of small molecules through amorphous dense membranes by increasing the tortuosity [38,40]. Nevertheless, their relatively polar surface has been reported to promote the transport of polar species such as water through non-polar matrices, presumably by creating polar transport channels at the nanocellulose-nonpolar matrix interface [19,40–44] as anticipated for matrix-incompatible fillers [45]. Recently, a straightforward solvent casting-evaporation method that allows the preparation of nanocomposite membranes that feature a compositional gradient in the direction transversal to the membrane plane (i.e., cross-sectional gradient) was reported [19,44]. The process exploits the inherent instability of colloidal suspensions of CNCs in tetrahydrofuran (THF), and their gravitational sedimentation after casting mixtures of CNCs and the hydrophobic polymer of poly(styrene)-*block*-poly

(butadiene)-*block*-poly(styrene) (SBS) as matrix. The compositionally graded architecture was shown to render the water transport characteristics of these membranes asymmetric, with preferential water diffusion from the CNC-rich towards the CNC-free side [44].

We now set out to explore the effect of such compositional asymmetry on the separation of a model ethanol-water mixture containing 10 wt% ethanol, a typical concentration of ethanol in fermentation broths, by pervaporation [5,6]. Such asymmetric structures could not easily be obtained by merely blending the SBS with a hydrophobic small molecule or polymer. As in our previous studies [19,44], we used SBS as the matrix for the CNCs, due to its excellent film forming properties, the mechanical and solvent robustness of this material, and the promising pervaporation performance of SBS towards ethanol as demonstrated by earlier studies [46–52]. Additionally, the CNCs were modified using hydrophobic oleic acid moieties (OLA-CNCs) to investigate the effect of surface chemistry. This modification allowed us to increase the compatibility of CNCs with the non-polar SBS matrix and investigate the impact of the surface groups of CNCs on the separation performance of the nanocomposites. Several organic acids and acid chlorides have been previously employed to decorate covalently the surface of cellulosic (nano)materials [53–56], including oleic acid, a readily available inexpensive fatty acid. We here show that the SBS/OLA-CNC membranes display increased net fluxes of ethanol, while their separation properties are comparable to those of the reference SBS membranes. Thus, by simply modifying the surface chemistry of CNCs, the pervaporation properties and the degree of asymmetric mass transport can be tailored.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Poly(styrene)-*block*-poly(butadiene)-*block*-poly(styrene) (SBS) (30 wt% styrene, density $\delta = 0.94 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$, $M_w \sim 140,000 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$), sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 ; 95–98%), pyridine (Py; anhydrous, 99.8%), *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride (TsCl; $\geq 98\%$), and oleic acid (i.e., *cis*-9-octadecenoic acid; OLA; \geq

90%) were acquired from Sigma-Aldrich and not further purified. Ethanol (EtOH; absolute, >99%) and Tetrahydrofuran (THF; 99.5%) were purchased from Fisher Scientific. Deionized (DI) water from the house system was used.

2.2. Preparation of nanoparticles and nanocomposite membranes

2.2.1. Isolation of CNCs and preparation of oleic acid-modified CNCs (OLA-CNCs)

Cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) were isolated using a standard protocol from Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The process is a modification of the protocol originally developed by Gray and co-workers [57,58] and involves hydrolysis with sulfuric acid (64 wt%, 45 min, 45 °C) [19,44]. The analysis of transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images (120 CNCs from 5 images, Appendix A.1.1.) with ImageJ allowed determining the average length (128 ± 55 nm), width (14 ± 4 nm), and aspect ratio (9 ± 3) of the CNCs [44]. The concentration of the sulfate half-ester groups was determined to be 254 mmol kg^{-1} using conductometric titration [44]. A procedure reported by Uschanov and co-workers [55] was adapted for the preparation of oleic acid-modified CNCs (OLA-CNCs) using an esterification strategy proposed earlier by Brewster and Ciotti [59]. More specifically, *p*-toluenesulfonyl chloride (3.5 g from a freshly opened bottle) and oleic acid (5 mL) were combined in a 50 mL three-necked round-bottomed flask at room temperature. To this mixture, freeze-dried CNCs (0.5 g) were added and the flask was flushed with nitrogen for 10 min before dry pyridine (15 mL) was added. Immediately after the addition, the color of the dispersion turned dark yellow. The mixture was purged with nitrogen and stirred for 2 h after reaching a temperature of 50 °C. Subsequently, the reaction mixture was quenched by adding 50:50 v:v aqueous ethanol (30 mL), and the precipitated nanoparticles were collected by filtration. The precipitate was washed with ethanol and water on a glass filter and transferred into an extraction thimble. After a 24 h Soxhlet extraction process with ethanol, the product was dried under ambient conditions in a fume hood. The isolated white solid product (OLA-CNCs) was dispersed in THF at a concentration of 0.5 wt% for the preparation of the nanocomposites. The OLA-CNCs were characterized using ATR-IR spectroscopy, CHONS elemental analysis, wide-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) (see Appendix A.1.3.), colloidal stability measurements (see Appendix A.1.4.) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) (see Appendix A.1.5.).

2.2.2. Preparation of SBS/CNC and SBS/OLA-CNC nanocomposite membranes by solvent casting-evaporation

Self-standing nanocomposite membranes were produced according to a reported method that was slightly modified [19,44]. SBS pellets and stock suspensions of CNCs or OLA-CNCs in THF (0.5 wt%) were combined in a round-bottomed flask so that the weight fraction of the nanoparticles in the final nanocomposite was 8, 15 or 22 wt%. In all cases, THF was added until reaching a final SBS concentration of 1.6 wt% in THF. For example, 255 mg of SBS were combined with 9.0 g of a 0.5 wt% OLA-CNC suspension (45 mg OLA-CNCs) and diluted further with 7.3 g of THF to prepare SBS/OLA-CNC 22 wt% composite membranes. The flasks were sealed, the suspensions were stirred for 30 min at room temperature, followed by sonication of the suspensions in a sonication bath (Sonoswiss SW3H ultrasonic bath) equipped with a water cooling system. The mixtures were then poured into preheated poly (tetrafluoroethylene) Petri dishes with an internal diameter of 10.2 cm, which were subsequently placed for 6 h into a ventilated oven kept at 50 °C to evaporate the solvent. After 6 h, the Petri dishes were removed from the oven and allowed to cool to ambient. All of the membranes were self-standing and not tacky. The above protocol afforded membranes with a thickness of $\sim 33 \mu\text{m}$, as determined using a digital micrometer (IP 65, Mitutoyo) at random spots ($n = 10$). All of the membranes were stored in a dust-free environment at ambient conditions (23 °C, 40% RH) prior to any measurements unless otherwise

stated.

2.3. Characterization of CNCs and OLA-CNCs nanoparticles

2.3.1. ATR-FTIR spectroscopy

Fourier transform (FT) infrared spectroscopy (IR) was used to characterize the CNCs after the esterification process. IR-spectra of neat CNCs, oleic acid (OLA) and OLA-CNCs were collected with a Perkin Elmer Spectrum 65 spectrometer in Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR) mode (Universal ATR model, $\sim 1.7 \mu\text{m}$ depth of penetration). A total of 8 scans at a 4 cm^{-1} resolution and a wavenumber range of $4000\text{--}600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ were acquired per sample.

2.3.2. Degree of substitution (DS) with elemental analysis

The samples were analyzed by the Microelemental Analysis lab, ETH Zürich for their C, H, N, O and S content (LECO TruSpec Micro for C, H and N, LECO 628 – O for O and HEKAtech Eurovector for S content). The bulk degree of substitution (DS_{bulk}) was calculated using equation (1) [60]:

$$DS_{\text{bulk}} = \frac{72.07 - C \times 162.14}{265.46 \times C - 216.19} \quad (1)$$

where C represents the relative mass fraction of carbon in the OLA-CNCs, and the values 72.07, 162.14, 265.46, and 216.19 correspond to the carbon content of one anhydroglucose unit (6×12.011), the molar mass of anhydroglucose units, the molar mass of the OLA moieties (282.47-17.007) and the carbon content of the OLA moieties (18×12.011), respectively. The degree of substitution at the surface of the nanoparticles (DS_s) was calculated by dividing the DS_{bulk} value with the chain ratio (R_c) (i.e., the ratio of available chains at the surface of the particles to the total number of chains) using equation (2) as proposed previously by Eyley and Thielemans [32]:

$$DS_s = \frac{DS_{\text{bulk}}}{R_c} \quad (2)$$

The chain ratio R_c can be calculated with equation (3) [32]:

$$R_c = 2 \left(\frac{d_{(1\bar{1}0)}}{L_1} + \frac{d_{(110)}}{L_2} \right) \quad (3)$$

where L_1 and L_2 are the width and height of the crystal (assuming a rectangular surface geometry, then $L_1 = L_2$ and can be determined with TEM using the average width of the crystals), and $d_{(1\bar{1}0)}$ and $d_{(110)}$ correspond to the d-spacings of the lattice planes $1\bar{1}0$ (~ 0.61 nm) and 110 (~ 0.53 nm) of cellulose I β , respectively [61]. The theoretical maximum amount of accessible hydroxyl groups that can be modified on an anhydroglucose unit is 1.5, because only three hydroxyl groups out of six for every two anhydroglucose units face the crystal's surface [32]. Therefore, the percentage of surface substitution, SSub, can be determined using equation (4):

$$\text{SSub}\% = \frac{DS_s}{1.5} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

2.3.3. Wide-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS)

WAXS data were acquired with a Rigaku Innovative Technologies NanoMax-IQ camera at room temperature using dried powders of CNCs and OLA-CNCs. The 2D SAXS patterns were averaged radially to obtain 1D WAXS curves of $I(q)$ vs q (scattering vector $q = 4\pi\lambda^{-1}\sin(\theta/2)$, with θ corresponding to the scattering angle and $\lambda = 0.1524$ nm to the X-ray wavelength). To convert the scattering vector q into 2θ values, we used Mathematica (Wolfram Research, Inc.). OLA-CNCs were mounted between Kapton® sheets. To obtain the Kapton-free signal of OLA-CNCs, the WAXS spectrum of Kapton® and a 2θ -dependent quadratic polynomial as a smoothing factor were used. The relative degree of crystallinity ($C.I.$) of CNCs and OLA-CNCs was estimated by utilizing the

intensity-method of Segal (equation (5)) [62]:

$$C.I. = \frac{I_{002} - I_{AM}}{I_{002}} \quad (5)$$

where I_{002} corresponds to the intensity of the 002 lattice diffraction peak ($\sim 22.3^\circ$) and I_{AM} to the intensity of the “amorphous” (less-ordered) regions of the sample detected at $\sim 18^\circ$.

2.4. Characterization of the nanocomposite SBS/CNC and SBS/OLA-CNC membranes

2.4.1. Verification of the nanocomposite membrane's transversal heterogeneity by ATR-IR spectroscopy

Fourier transform (FT) Attenuated Total Reflection (ATR) Infrared (IR) spectra of the membranes were collected with a PerkinElmer Spectrum 65 spectrometer (Universal ATR model, $\sim 1.7 \mu\text{m}$ depth of penetration). IR-spectra were acquired (5 scans, 4 cm^{-1} resolution) using both sides (upper side, US, and bottom side, BS during casting) of the membranes to investigate the signal intensity variations of bands corresponding to CNCs and OLA-CNCs.

2.4.2. Verification of the transversal heterogeneity of the nanocomposite membranes by Raman microscopy

To further monitor the transversal heterogeneity of the nanocomposite membranes, maps of the cross-sectional distribution of CNCs and OLA-CNCs at the membranes using Raman microscopy were recorded. The samples were imbibed in 10 mL ethanol-filled plastic syringes, immersed in liquid nitrogen followed by cryo-fracturing of the syringes containing the membranes using a pincer. Cross-sections of the membranes were secured between glass slides and tested in a HORIBA Jobin Yvon LabRAM HR800 Raman microprobe spectrometer (polarized 633 nm excitation laser, 800 mm focal length; spectral window $400\text{--}4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; spectral resolution 0.3 cm^{-1} ; 50x objective). The number of accumulations per spectrum was set to 5, their duration to 5 s, and the laser intensity to 20 mW. Mapping of the nanocellulose (CNCs or OLA-CNCs) content in the membranes was conducted by acquiring spectra at the cross-section at five positions (0, 25, 50, 75 and 100% of the total thickness; bottom side (BS) $x = 0\%$; upper side (US) $x = 100\%$). Five replicates ($n = 5$) per spot ($5 \times 5 = 25$ total unique spots) were acquired to track the signal variation. The LabSpec 6 software (HORIBA Scientific) was used to collect the Raman spectra, and was also employed to smoothen the raw data and apply a baseline correction. To track the nanocellulose content at the cross-section, we determined the relative concentration of nanocellulose (RCN) at each spot using equation (6):

$$RCN = \frac{I_{1096}}{I_{1096} + I_{1201}} \quad (6)$$

where I_{1096} and I_{1201} correspond to the baseline-corrected absolute signals ascribed to nanocellulose (C-O stretching) [63,64] and SBS (CH_2 bending) [65], respectively. Box charts of the calculated RCN as a function of the relative distance from the bottom side (BS) were created using Origin (OriginLab). In all box charts, whiskers extend to min and max values, box edges show 25–75 percentiles, center lines represent medians, and hollow squares represents means.

2.4.3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

To image the cross-sections, membranes were placed in ethanol-filled syringes and subsequently cryo-fractured in liquid nitrogen using a pincer to reveal their cross-sections. Parts of the membranes were dried under a flow of nitrogen before they were attached to the carbon tape with the upper side (US) of the membranes exposed towards the tape. The samples were sputter-coated with a 2 nm thick gold layer using a Cressington 208HR High Resolution sputter coater. SEM images of the membranes were acquired in secondary electron mode at 7 kV using a Tescan Mira3 LM FE scanning electron microscope.

2.4.4. Polarized optical microscopy (POM)

The membranes were visualized in transmission mode between crossed polarizers with an optical microscope (Olympus BX51), and pictures were taken with a DP72 digital camera. To acquire the reported images, we used a 20x objective lens. All of the membranes had a thickness of $\sim 33 \mu\text{m}$.

2.4.5. Pervaporation experiments

Pervaporation experiments were conducted at 40°C with an ethanol-water feed containing 10 wt% of ethanol. A custom-made pervaporation setup that was previously described (Appendix A. Fig. A.6) was used [19]. The flat-sheet nanocomposite membranes were mounted between Viton O-rings in a membrane cell having a permeation area of $3.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}^2$ (TECH INC, India). To mechanically support the membranes, a stainless steel grid and a porous poly(acrylonitrile) (PAN) membrane filter ($0.2 \mu\text{m}$) (Sterlitech, U.S.A.) were used. The feed was constantly recirculated with a peristaltic pump (RH-P120S, Ravel Hiteks Pvt Ltd, India). On the opposite side of the membranes, a vacuum pump (SVT8, Swiss Vacuum Technologies, Switzerland) was used to retain the pressure below 3 mbar. The permeate was collected in two glass traps using liquid nitrogen for at least three data points after reaching a steady state (~ 2 h) and the mass of the permeates was determined gravimetrically using a balance (ML204/01, Mettler Toledo). The ethanol concentration of the permeates was analyzed with an Abbe refractometer (ORT 1RS, KERN & Sohn, Germany) controlled at 25°C with a Peltier thermostat (PT31, KRÜSS, Germany) (see Appendix A. Fig. A.7 for calibration curve). The mean and standard deviation values of at least two experiments ($n = 2$) per membrane composition are reported. Mass fluxes were determined as follows (equation (7)):

$$\hat{J}_i = \frac{J_i}{A} \quad (7)$$

where \hat{J}_i represents the permeation area (A) normalized mass flux (J_i) of the permeating species i . The mass flux, J_i , was calculated by linear regression of the measured mass-time data and the mass concentration, m_i^p , of each component at the permeate. The total mass flux, J , of the process was normalized with the membrane thickness (ℓ) and the permeation area (A) to calculate thickness-normalized permeation rates (NPR) (equation (8)):

$$NPR = \frac{J}{A} \ell \quad (8)$$

To calculate the permeability for each component i , equation (9) was used:

$$P_i = \frac{\hat{J}_i \ell}{p_{ir} - p_{il}} \quad (9)$$

where p_{ir} and p_{il} are the partial pressures of component i towards the retentate (p_{ir}) and the permeate side (p_{il}) of the membrane, respectively [66]. All permeability values are reported in SI units. Assuming negligible membrane polarization effects and unchanged feed composition, the partial pressure of each component towards the feed is then given by equation (10):

$$p_{ir} = \gamma_i^f x_i^f p_i^{sat} \quad (10)$$

where γ_i^f is the activity coefficient of component i for the utilized feed conditions (determination using UNIFAC and parameters adapted from Hansen and co-workers [67], Appendix A. Table A.4), x_i^f is the mole fraction of each component in the feed, and p_i^{sat} is the saturated vapor pressure determined by Antoine's equation (11):

$$\log_{10} p_i^{sat} = A_i - \frac{B_i}{C_i + T} \quad (11)$$

In equation (11), A_i , B_i , and C_i are constants that were adapted from

NIST (see Appendix A. Table A.5) and T corresponds to the temperature of the feed. The total pressure at the permeate side of the membrane was retained at low values (< 3 mbar) and therefore $p_{i,e}$ was not considered for the calculations [66]. The separation factor β_{ew} was calculated with equation (12), assuming that the retentate (i.e., feed) composition is practically constant in the time-scale of each experiment (< 60 h):

$$\beta_{ew} = \frac{\left(\frac{m_e^p}{m_w^p}\right)}{\left(\frac{m_e^r}{m_w^r}\right)} \quad (12)$$

where e and w represent ethanol and water, respectively, and m^p and m^r are the weight fractions of in the permeate and the feed. No separation is essentially achieved if $\beta_{ew} = 1$, where the composition of the permeate is the same as in the feed. Higher separation factors β_{ew} reflect better recovery of ethanol. To calculate the membrane selectivity α_{ew} , equation (13) was used:

$$\alpha_{ew} = \frac{P_e}{P_w} \quad (13)$$

where P_e and P_w correspond to the mass permeability of ethanol and water, respectively. For this mixture, a factor of 2.56 can be used to convert mass-based selectivity to molar-based selectivity [66]. A useful parameter to evaluate the membrane performance is the pervaporation separation index (PSI) [68] (equation (14)):

$$PSI = \hat{J}(\beta_{ew} - 1) \quad (14)$$

When $PSI = 0$, then the total flux $\hat{J} = 0$ and/or the separation factor $\beta_{ew} = 1$. Generally, a higher PSI translates to better pervaporation performances. To evaluate the effect of the compositional asymmetry of the membranes on permeability, we defined the permeability asymmetry factor (PAF) (equation (15)):

$$PAF = \frac{P_{iBS|US}}{P_{iUS|BS}} \quad (15)$$

where $P_{iBS|US}$ and $P_{iUS|BS}$ correspond to the permeability of component i through a membrane with the bottom (BS) (i.e., rich in nanocellulose) and the upper (US) (i.e., poor in nanocellulose) side (as defined by the membrane manufacturing process) exposed towards the feed mixture, respectively.

2.4.6. Water and ethanol uptake

Water and ethanol uptake were measured using the 15 wt% nanocomposite membranes prepared with either unmodified CNCs or OLA-CNCs. Before the swelling tests, the membranes were dried at 60 °C in an oven for 48 h under vacuum before their initial dry weight (M_o) was measured. Afterwards, the dry membranes were placed in sealed glass containers filled with either ethanol or water. The containers were subsequently transferred in an oven kept at 40 °C. After the samples had reached equilibrium swelling, they were removed from the containers, gently blotted dry with lab tissue paper and measured gravimetrically for their solvent-equilibrated mass (M_∞). The equilibrium solvent uptake was calculated as follows (equation (16)):

$$\text{Solvent uptake (\%)} = \frac{M_\infty - M_o}{M_o} \times 100 \quad (16)$$

2.4.7. Small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS)

SAXS data were acquired using the same instrumentation as for WAXS experiments (see Appendix A. Fig. A.8). The membranes ($\ell \sim 33$ μm) were mounted "as cast" without employing any annealing process.

The 2D SAXS patterns were averaged radially to obtain 1D SAXS curves of $I(q)$ vs q .

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of CNCs and OLA-CNCs

The CNCs were isolated from processed cotton using a well-established hydrolysis process using sulfuric acid (see Experimental Section 2.2.1). The unmodified CNCs had a length of 128 ± 55 nm, a width of 14 ± 4 nm, and an aspect ratio of 9 ± 3 . The concentration of hydrolysis-introduced sulfate half-ester groups was determined to be 254 mmol kg^{-1} by conductometric titration [44]. A previously reported procedure by Uschanov and co-workers [55], which in turn is based on an esterification strategy proposed earlier by Brewster and Ciotti [59], was used to prepare the oleic acid-modified CNCs (OLA-CNCs, Fig. 1a). The success of the reaction was verified by IR spectroscopy (Fig. 1b). In the case of OLA-CNCs, the formation of an ester bond ($-\text{COOR}$) was detected at 1746 cm^{-1} . This band was shifted towards higher frequencies compared to the carbonyl ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) stretching vibration of the neat oleic acid (1708 cm^{-1}) as previously observed after esterification reactions with fatty acids [69]. This shift is also in agreement with the IR spectra of fatty acid-functionalized cellulosic materials reported by Uschanov and co-workers [55]. Characteristic bands corresponding to cellulose were detected in the case of CNCs and OLA-CNCs such as $-\text{OH}$ stretching vibrations ($3650\text{--}3050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), as well as in the fingerprint region with C-O-C stretching (1162 cm^{-1}), glucose ring breathing (1110 cm^{-1}), C-O/C-C stretching ($1054, 1031$ and 984 cm^{-1}), and $-\text{OH}$ out of plane bending (665 cm^{-1}) vibrations (see also Appendix A. Table A.1) [70–72]. A weak *cis* $=\text{C-H}$ stretching vibration at 3005 cm^{-1} was observed in the case of OLA-CNCs derived from the unsaturated oleic acid chains [69]. Furthermore, sharp and strong bands at 2922 and 2853 cm^{-1} were detected corresponding to asymmetric stretching vibrations of the aliphatic CH_2 groups of oleic acid on CNCs [69].

Further evidence for the successful functionalization was obtained by elemental analyses, which allow a quantitative assessment of the bulk degree of substitution (DS_{bulk}) of CNCs with oleic acid. The relative percentages of C, H, O, N, and S were determined for both the neat and the modified CNCs from two different batches of OLA-CNCs (Table 1). The presence of sulfur atoms in both cases is ascribed to the sulfate ester groups that result from the acid hydrolysis isolation process of CNCs [73]. Using elemental analysis, the amount of sulfur was estimated to be $256 \pm 4 \text{ mmol kg}^{-1}$ of CNCs, which is in agreement with the amount of sulfate half-ester groups determined previously using conductometric titration (254 mmol kg^{-1}) [44] and with values reported by Beck and co-workers using similar acid-hydrolysis conditions [73]. In the case of OLA-CNCs, the hydroxyl groups were partially replaced by long alkyl chains of oleic acid. Thus, the content of C and H increased, whereas the content of O% and S% was reduced, in comparison to the neat CNCs. Using equation (1), the DS_{bulk} was calculated to be 0.32 ± 0.03 from the elemental analysis data of two OLA-CNC batches that had been prepared under the same conditions, which leads to a surface degree of substitution (DS_s) of 1.96. This value is slightly higher than the maximum expected DS_s value for CNCs of 1.5 [32], which we tentatively explain with an over-estimation of the dimensions of the crystals (L_1 and L_2), which in turn leads to an underestimation of R_c . Indeed, due to the formation of CNC-dimers ascribed to intermolecular hydrogen bonding, their width is routinely overestimated in microscopic analyses [74]. Assuming that the actual dimensions of the crystals are half of the determined mean width (i.e., crystals packed in couples) (size analysis of TEM images), we estimated the R_c value (determined using equation (3)) to be approximately doubled (0.33 vs 0.16) and the DS_s to be 0.98,

Fig. 1. (a) Reaction scheme of the oleic acid esterification of CNCs. Note that although only one primary hydroxyl group is shown to be modified with oleic acid, the degree of substitution determined suggests that most of the available hydroxyl groups — especially the primary ones — have been functionalized. (b) ATR-FTIR spectra of CNCs, oleic acid (OLA), and oleic acid-modified CNCs (OLA-CNCs) confirm the formation of an ester bond (1746 cm⁻¹). (c) Wide-angle X-ray scattering (WAXS) spectra of CNCs, oleic acid, and OLA-CNCs verifying the retention of the cellulosic crystalline structure upon surface modification.

Table 1

Elemental analyses of CNCs and OLA-CNCs show substantial increases in the carbon (C%) and hydrogen content (H%) in OLA-CNCs due the covalent attachment of oleic acid.

	C (%)	H (%)	O (%)	N (%)	S (%)
CNCs	41.52 ± 0.08	6.16 ± 0.00	50.62 ± 0.516	0.01 ± 0.00	0.82 ± 0.01
OLA-CNCs Batch A	57.70 ± 0.07	8.19 ± 0.06	33.33 ± 0.01	0.01 ± 0.00	0.44 ± 0.01
OLA-CNCs Batch B	56.77 ± 0.11	8.03 ± 0.01	33.14 ± 0.06	0.01 ± 0.00	0.48 ± 0.01

which corresponds to a surface substitution (SSub%) of 65% based on equation (4). Less probable explanations for an increased DS_s value are that a minor fraction of the much less reactive secondary alcohol groups on the surface has reacted, and the modification of primary hydroxyl groups that are buried within the crystals, which is not supported by the collected WAXS data (see Fig. 1c).

The surface functionalization of cellulosic nanomaterials usually requires harsh reaction conditions and, as a consequence, the crystalline structure of nanocellulose is in jeopardy of chemical degradation [32]. To explore if the surface modification affects the crystalline structure of CNCs, WAXS spectra of oleic acid, CNCs, and OLA-CNCs were acquired (Fig. 1c). In the case of oleic acid, a broad amorphous halo was detected ranging from 9 to 36° with a maximum at 19.7°. In the case of CNCs, the characteristic lattice diffraction peaks of cellulose I (101, 10 $\bar{1}$, 021, 002, 040) are observed. Using the intensity method of Segal and co-workers [62], the crystallinity index (C.I.) of the unmodified CNCs was determined to be ~84%, which is comparable to previously reported values

using similar CNC isolation processes [75]. In the case of OLA-CNCs, the characteristic diffraction peaks of cellulose I are also observed, as well as a slight broadening effect detected in the vicinity of the 10 $\bar{1}$ and 021 peaks (~17–19°) and at slightly higher angles than the 002 diffraction peak (~23–26°), matching the broad oleic acid WAXS pattern. Subtraction of the amorphous oleic acid WAXS signal from the OLA-CNC spectrum confirmed the retention of all the characteristic cellulose I diffraction peaks. By using the subtracted curve, we estimated the C.I. of OLA-CNCs to be ~83% (Segal method). This suggests that the crystalline morphology of the cellulosic nanocrystals was preserved from the modification process.

3.2. Characterization of the nanocomposite SBS/CNC and SBS/OLA-CNC membranes

Our group and others have previously reported that the sedimentation of CNCs during solvent casting-evaporation processes allows one to create nanocomposite membranes that exhibit a compositional gradient of CNCs in the transversal direction [19,44,76]. To confirm that the here-studied membranes feature a similar asymmetric architecture, we used ATR-IR spectroscopy to acquire spectra of both sides of the nanocomposite membranes (Fig. 2a). The terms “upper” (US) and “bottom” (BS) side are used to distinguish the two membrane sides as defined by the casting process. Gratifyingly, the ATR-IR spectra confirm a clear compositional contrast between the upper (US) and bottom (BS) sides of the membranes in both the SBS/CNC and the SBS/OLA-CNC membranes. In the case of the SBS/CNC membranes, bands corresponding to CNCs were absent or very weak in the spectra acquired at the US (the measurement probes the surface with a penetration depth of ~1.7 μm). By

Fig. 2. (a) ATR-IR spectra acquired at the bottom (BS) and the upper (US) surfaces of the membranes displaying the compositional asymmetry of the SBS/CNC and SBS/OLA-CNC 15 wt% nanocomposites. The characteristic vibration bands at 1110 cm⁻¹ (★) (glucose ring breathing) and 1746 cm⁻¹ (●) (C=O ester stretching vibration) were highlighted to track the relative concentration of CNCs and OLA-CNCs in the nanocomposites, respectively. (b) Box plot displaying the relative concentration of nanocellulose (RCN) as function of transversal position ($n = 5$ in each position) in SBS/CNC 15% and SBS/OLA-CNC 15% membranes determined by Raman microscopy. Whiskers extend to min and max values, box edges mark 25–75 percentiles, center lines represent medians, and hollow squares represent means. The dashed line and grey band correspond to the mean \pm s.d. ($n = 3$ in each position) of the RCC of the SBS reference. I_{1096} and I_{1201} correspond to the baseline-corrected absolute signals attributed to nanocellulose (C-O stretching) [63,64] and SBS (CH₂ bending) [65], respectively.

contrast, the ATR-IR spectrum collected at the BS of the SBS/CNC membranes is rich in cellulose-related bands such as –OH stretching (3650–3050 cm⁻¹), –OH in plane bending (1336 cm⁻¹), C-O-C stretching (1162 cm⁻¹), glucose ring breathing (1110 and 897 cm⁻¹), C-O/C-C stretching (1054, 1031 and 984 cm⁻¹), and –OH out of plane bending (665 cm⁻¹) vibrations (see also Appendix A, Table A1 for band-assignment).

In the case of the SBS/OLA-CNC membranes, bands of OLA-CNCs are distinguishable in the ATR-IR spectra of both membrane surfaces, although the intensity of these bands is more pronounced in the BS than the US spectra. For example, the absorption ratio A_{1746}/A_{697} (1746 cm⁻¹: C=O stretching vibration of the ester bond of OLA-CNCs and 697 cm⁻¹: out-of plane bending of C-H of the SBS' phenyl rings) was determined to be 0.11 and 0.03 for the BS and the US of SBS/OLA-CNC, respectively. On account of the polarity differences between CNCs and OLA-CNCs, we ascribed this behavior to an improved compatibility of the OLA-CNCs with THF as well as the matrix, leading to less pronounced sedimentation of OLA-CNCs and a better dispersion in SBS in comparison to the unmodified CNCs.

To investigate the distribution of CNCs and OLA-CNCs along the cross-section of the membranes in more detail, Raman microscopy was employed to track the spatial intensity variation of bands associated with nanocellulose (C-O stretching; 1096 cm⁻¹) and SBS (CH₂ bending; 1201 cm⁻¹) along the transversal direction of the membranes (Fig. 2b, see also Supplementary Information Fig. A. 10). We expressed the relative concentration of nanocellulose (RCN) as the ratio of the intensities of these signals (see equation (6)). The Raman data show clearly that the RCN decreases from the bottom (BS) towards the upper side (US) for both types of nanocellulose-containing membranes (Fig. 2b). This decrease of RCN is indicative of a higher relative concentration of nanocellulose towards the bottom side (BS) of the membranes and confirms the ATR-IR data acquired on the two sides of the composites (Fig. 2a). A comparison shows that the RCN appears to change in a steeper manner in the case of SBS/CNC 15% than in the SBS/OLA-CNC 15% membranes, which implies a more pronounced compositional gradient in the SBS/CNC composites (Fig. 2b).

Further evidence for the cross-sectional compositional asymmetry of the membranes was obtained by scanning electron microscopy (Fig. 3a–c). In our previous studies, we observed that the roughness at the cross-section of cryo-fractured SBS/CNC membranes increased as we

approached the bottom side of the membranes [19,44]. Similarly, it is evident that the bottom side of the SBS/CNC 15% membranes (Fig. 3b) is notably rougher than the upper side of the membrane resembling the smooth cross-section of the neat SBS membranes (Fig. 3a). This is in agreement with the way the membranes were mounted on the SEM substrates (i.e., upper side — poor in CNCs side — of the membranes adhered on the carbon tape). Regarding the SBS/OLA-CNC 15% membranes, the morphology of the cross-section was more homogeneous in comparison to that of the SBS/CNC membranes (Fig. 3c), which confirms the ATR-IR and Raman microscopy data (Fig. 2), i.e., that the concentration gradient is less pronounced in the case of the OLA-CNC membranes (Fig. 1b). Previously, Dufresne and co-workers have observed similar inhomogeneous cross-sectional morphologies in cryo-fractured natural rubber-CNC composites using SEM [76].

Regarding the distribution of CNCs and OLA-CNCs along the main membrane planes, we used polarized optical microscopy to qualitatively assess the homogeneity of the samples (Fig. 3d–f). The neat SBS samples were optically isotropic (Fig. 3d), whereas the SBS/CNC 15 wt% (Fig. 3e) and SBS/OLA-CNC 15 wt% (Fig. 3f) nanocomposites displayed homogeneously distributed birefringent domains across the whole membrane area. In the case of SBS/OLA-CNC samples, the birefringent domains were less pronounced compared to the SBS/CNC samples. This behavior may be attributed to the higher affinity of OLA-CNCs with THF, which may have incited a better dispersion of the fillers in the SBS matrix during solvent casting-evaporation.

Previously, we demonstrated that the compositionally graded architecture of the SBS/CNC nanocomposite membranes rendered the water permeation properties directional, with increased permeation when the CNC-rich bottom side was facing the donor (i.e., feed) [44]. This asymmetry was more pronounced as the cellulose content was increased from 0 to 15 wt%, at which point a permeation asymmetry factor (PAF) of 1.4 was reached. Here we report on the pervaporation properties of such composites containing either 15 wt% of CNCs or OLA-CNCs.

SBS is an inherently hydrophobic polymer with a low water uptake (<0.15% at 25 °C) [19,44]. Nevertheless, it displays a relatively high permeability that is primarily attributed to the rubbery poly(butadiene) domains [77]. Swelling experiments show that the neat SBS membranes exhibit a higher affinity towards ethanol (equilibrium swelling ~1.0%) than water (~0.2%) (Fig. 4). Upon incorporation of the polar CNCs (15

Fig. 3. (a–c) SEM cross-section images of (a) SBS neat, (b) SBS/CNC 15 wt%, (c) SBS/OLA-CNC 15 wt% membranes (scale bars: 10 μm). We indicate the bottom and upper side of the as cast membranes with the acronyms BS and US, respectively. (d–f) Polarized optical microscopy (POM) images under crossed-polarizers of the main membrane planes: (d) SBS neat, (e) SBS/CNC 15 wt%, (f) SBS/OLA-CNC 15 wt% (scale bars: 100 μm). Note the presence of non-birefringent black domains at the bottom right corner of the images demonstrating the edge of the membrane.

Fig. 4. Plot showing the equilibrium solvent mass uptake (%) (i.e., swelling degree) of water and ethanol at 40 °C of the nanocomposite membranes.

wt%) in SBS, water and ethanol uptake increased notably, reaching a mean solvent uptake of $\sim 3.4\%$ and $\sim 3.5\%$ for ethanol and water, respectively (Fig. 4). In the case of the 15 wt% OLA-CNC composite, the solvent uptake was considerably different for ethanol and water, with respective uptakes of $\sim 2.8\%$ and 1.2% (Fig. 4).

In pervaporation processes, the relative uptake and diffusion of the penetrants by and through the membranes govern the observed permeation properties. In the SBS/CNC nanocomposites, there is — in principle — a competition between an increasing swelling degree (i.e., affinity of the membrane towards polar species) and a more tortuous diffusion pathway formed by the semi-crystalline particles (i.e., CNCs), which presumably allow transport only along their surface. To assess the impact of nanocellulose on the permeation properties of the nanocomposites, a mixture of ethanol and water (10 wt % ethanol) at 40 °C was used as a simplified model feed. This composition is typically employed to mimic the concentration of ethanol in aqueous fermentation broths [5,6]. Using these feed conditions, we investigated the pervaporation performance of the nanocomposite SBS/CNC and SBS/OLA-CNC membranes. In terms of fluxes, both ethanol and water flow increased upon incorporation of the polar CNCs into the SBS matrix and exposure of the CNC-rich side (BS) towards the feed (Fig. 5a). However, the relative increase of the water flux (172%) was considerably higher than that of ethanol (51%) in comparison to the respective

Fig. 5. Plots displaying (a) the mass flux of water and ethanol, (b) the collected weight fraction of ethanol at the permeate side (yellow line indicates feed conditions), (c) the process separation factor, β (yellow line at $\beta = 1$ indicates the minimum value for an ethanol-enriching process), (d) the membrane selectivity, α , towards ethanol (yellow line at $\alpha = 1$ indicative of when the membrane changes from ethanol-to water-selective and vice-versa), (e) the pervaporation separation index (*PSI*) and (f) the permeability asymmetry factor (*PAF*) as a function of nanocellulose type incorporated in SBS and the exposed side of the membranes (BS: bottom side, US: upper side) towards the liquid feed mixture (feed conditions: 10 wt% ethanol, 40 °C) (yellow line at $PAF = 1$ corresponds to perfectly symmetric permeation properties regardless of the exposure side of the membrane towards the feed). Reported values are the mean and standard deviation of $n = 2$ measurements. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

fluxes through the neat SBS. The incorporation of CNCs in the SBS resulted in a lower ethanol purity in the permeate ($26 \pm 1\%$) in comparison to the neat SBS membranes ($38 \pm 1\%$) (Fig. 5b), thus lowering the separation factor from 5.6 to 3.1 (Fig. 5c) and the selectivity from 1.15 to 0.64 (Fig. 5d). It has to be noted here that during the timescale of the experiment (< 60 h), the concentration of the feed (i.e., retentate) remains practically unchanged (~ 10 wt% ethanol) due to the use of an excess of ethanol and water in the feed (1500 g).

Similar effects on the separation factor and ethanol selectivity are observed for experiments in which the CNC-poor upper side (US) of the SBS/CNC membranes was exposed to the feed (Fig. 5c-d). Nevertheless, the overall flux was notably lowered in this configuration (i.e., upper membrane side towards the feed) in comparison to all other samples, both with and without nanocellulose (Fig. 5a). For example, the total flux was decreased by 25% compared to the neat SBS with flux decreases

of 8% and 54% for water and ethanol, respectively. In this configuration, the CNC-poor side (US) of the SBS/CNC composites limits the uptake of the two solutes, since the membrane-feed interface consists primarily of SBS. In this case, the crystalline and essentially impermeable CNCs appear to increase the tortuosity, thus elongating the diffusion pathways at the matrix-filler interface and reducing the overall fluxes.

In the case of the OLA-CNC membranes in the configuration with the OLA-CNC-rich side (BS) facing the feed, the separation factor β_{ew} and the selectivity α_{ew} of the membranes remained virtually unchanged compared to the neat SBS ($\beta_{ew} = 5.8 \pm 0.1$ vs 5.6 ± 0.3 and $\alpha_{ew} = 1.18 \pm 0.02$ vs 1.15 ± 0.06) (Fig. 5c-d), whereas the total flux increased to an intermediate value (38.0 ± 0.8 g h⁻¹ m⁻²) between that of the neat SBS (32.5 ± 0.1 g h⁻¹ m⁻²) and the SBS/CNC membrane with 15 wt% CNCs (73.4 ± 0.4 g h⁻¹ m⁻²) (Fig. 5a). Dense membranes exhibit usually a trade-off between permeability and selectivity [14,78]. Thus, an

increased flux is usually achieved at the expense of a decreased concentration of the preferentially recovered species at the permeate side, as observed for the SBS/CNC membranes with 15 wt% CNCs with the CNC-rich side facing the feed. Interestingly, the SBS/OLA-CNC 15 wt% - BS membranes do not follow this trend; the selectivity a_{ew} (1.18 ± 0.02) was similar to that of the neat SBS (1.15 ± 0.06 , Fig. 5d), while the permeability (and also the net fluxes) of ethanol was increased by 23% (3.48×10^{-14} vs 2.84×10^{-14} kg m⁻² s⁻¹ Pa⁻¹). Thus, the modification of the surface of CNCs with oleic acid enhances the transport of semi-polar species such as ethanol without deteriorating the separation factor β_{ew} and the selectivity a_{ew} . When the upper side (US) of SBS/OLA-CNC nanocomposite membrane faced the feed, a similar separation performance was observed ($\beta_{ew} = 5.8 \pm 0.1$ vs 5.6 ± 0.3 and $a_{ew} = 1.18 \pm 0.01$). However, the total flux through the SBS/OLA-CNC - US (31.7 ± 1.0 g h⁻¹ m⁻²) was essentially unchanged in comparison to the neat SBS (32.5 ± 1.3 g h⁻¹ m⁻²). This behavior suggests that the OLA-CNCs are not evenly distributed at the transversal direction of the membranes (as also supported by IR spectra on both SBS/OLA-CNC membrane sides and Raman microscopy at the cross-section of the membranes (Fig. 2)) resulting in asymmetric transport properties, as in the case of the SBS/CNC composites.

To evaluate the best performing membranes, we analyzed the data using the pervaporation separation index (*PSI*) (Fig. 5e) [68]. The mixed-matrix membranes incorporating 15 wt% OLA-CNCs exposed with their bottom side (BS) towards the feed presented the highest *PSI* with a value of 181 ± 8 g h⁻¹ m⁻². For comparison, the neat SBS and SBS/CNC 15% membranes exhibit a *PSI* of 151 ± 9 and 156 ± 21 g h⁻¹ m⁻², respectively. The SBS/CNC membranes demonstrate notably enhanced fluxes due to the introduction of polar sorption sites upon CNC incorporation, although these enhanced fluxes resulted in a lower separation factor β_{ew} . Conversely, the modification of CNCs with oleic acid retained the separation factor β_{ew} to similar levels as the neat SBS membranes, but a simultaneous increase in fluxes resulted in a higher *PSI* value. The least attractive performance was observed for the SBS/CNC nanocomposite with 15 wt% CNCs when the CNC-free side was exposed to the feed (44 ± 8 g h⁻¹ m⁻²). In this case, we observed a reduction of ethanol and water fluxes, but also a lower separation factor β_{ew} .

The observation that the transport properties of the nanocomposite membranes depend on the exposure side towards the feed mixture highlights the importance of controlling the transversal distribution of fillers in dense mixed-matrix (i.e., composite) membranes relying on a solution-diffusion mass transport mechanism. Asymmetric permeation properties of layered or compositionally graded composite membranes presenting pressure-dependent permeability constants were reported by Rogers and co-workers as early as 1957 [79], and later by Peterlin [80] and Petropoulos [81]. To quantify the transport asymmetry of the nanocomposite membranes, we used the permeability asymmetry factor (*PAF*) defined as the ratio of the mass permeabilities through the same membrane exposed with the bottom (BS) and the upper side (US) towards the feed. As shown in Fig. 5f, a clear permeation contrast for both ethanol and water is observed for the SBS/CNC nanocomposite (*PAF* ~ 3.36). Similar directional water transport characteristics (highest *PAF* ~ 2.53) were reported earlier by our group using SBS/CNC nanocomposites and water permeation experiments based on gravimetric cup techniques and determination of the diffusion of radiolabeled water [44]. In the previous study, it was demonstrated that nanocellulose provide polar sorption sites and drive the transport directionality in SBS/CNC nanocomposites [44]. By replacing the polar surface groups of nanocellulose with oleic acid in this study, it was anticipated that the permeation contrast for both ethanol and water would potentially diminish. Indeed, the SBS/CNC nanocomposite exhibits almost no transport asymmetry (*PAF* ~ 1.15) and the reference neat SBS membranes show completely isotropic transport characteristics for both permeating species (*PAF* ~ 1.00). The reduction of the *PAF* in the case of SBS/OLA-CNC membranes can be attributed to a less pronounced

transversal concentration gradient of OLA-CNCs (Fig. 5), as also supported by the acquired ATR-IR spectra and the Raman microscopy data (Fig. 2). Moreover, the partial decoration of the -OH groups of CNCs with the relatively non-polar oleic acid decreased the available sorption sites at the CNC surface. These findings are also consistent with the water wetting properties of the SBS/CNC and SBS/OLA-CNC nanocomposites (Appendix A.3.3). A stronger compositional asymmetry across the thickness of the membranes and the utilization of materials with a higher contrast in terms of sorption or resistance to diffusion could in principle lead to an even more pronounced asymmetric transport [80,81].

To systematically investigate the effect of the nanocellulose concentration on the pervaporation performance of the nanocomposites, SBS/CNC and SBS/OLA-CNC membranes with three filler concentrations (8, 15, and 22 wt%) were prepared. These experiments were carried out with the nanocellulose-rich bottom side of the membranes facing the feed. In terms of permeability, the OLA-CNC membranes demonstrated their best performance with an OLA-CNC content of 15 wt%. A slight decline of the permeability was observed with the SBS/OLA-CNC 22 wt% composite, potentially due to a further increase of the tortuosity (Fig. 6b). The membrane selectivity a_{ew} was retained at a similar level as the neat SBS and the total pervaporation performance was overall improved upon addition of OLA-CNCs (Fig. 6b). Conversely, the water permeability increased monotonically as a function of the CNC content at the expense of a reduced membrane selectivity a_{ew} for the CNC composites (Fig. 6a). This trend is somewhat expected, since — in principle — the affinity of the amphiphilic neat CNCs towards water is presumably higher than to ethanol. In terms of separation performance, the separation factor of the OLA-CNC membranes is relatively steady (β_{ew} of ~ 5.6), whereas the addition of unmodified CNCs resulted in a systematic reduction of the separation factor β_{ew} from ~ 5.6 (0% CNCs, neat SBS) to as low as ~ 2.1 (22% CNCs) (Appendix A.2.5).

To ensure that the observed permeation differences were the result of the nanofiller addition and not a matrix effect due to a varying phase segregation of the SBS' blocks as previously reported (see also discussion SI. 2 – SAXS section) [49,50], we carried out small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) experiments of the membranes (see Appendix A.3.1), which show that the incorporation of unmodified or oleic acid-modified CNCs into SBS had an imperceptible impact on the block copolymer morphology. Consequently, the permeation differences of the membranes reported in this study can be attributed to a different swelling degree and membrane tortuosity caused by CNCs of varying surface polarity rather than the phase segregation behavior of the SBS matrix itself.

In comparison to benchmark polymers (e.g., poly(dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS), poly(1-trimethylsilyl-1-propyne) (PTMSP)) [11], all of the membranes reported here exhibit lower thickness-normalized permeation rates *NPR* and separation factors β_{ew} , irrespective of the nanocellulose content and the side exposed to the feed. Under the same feed conditions (i.e., a binary ethanol-water mixture with a 10 wt% ethanol concentration at 40 °C), PDMS has been reported to display a thickness-normalized permeation rate *NPR* ranging between 4.5 and 10 kg μm^{-2} h⁻¹, as well as a separation factor β_{ew} of 7.5–9 [82,83]. PTMSP offers even more impressive properties, with a *NPR* of ~ 15.0 kg μm^{-2} h⁻¹ and a separation factor β_{ew} of ~ 15.2 [84], although its separation performance deteriorates with time due to ageing [85]. The SBS-nanocellulose membranes investigated here display *NPR*s between 0.8 and 4.4 kg μm^{-2} h⁻¹ and exhibit separation factors β_{ew} between 2.8 and 5.8 depending on the nanocellulose type, the filler concentration, and the exposure side towards the feed. These values are consistent with our earlier findings using SBS/CNF nanocomposites (1.0–3.0 kg μm^{-2} h⁻¹ and β_{ew} between 3.1 and 5.4) [19]. It is noted that the SBS matrix employed displays an inferior pervaporation performance (*NPR* ~ 1.0 kg μm^{-2} h⁻¹, β_{ew} ~ 5.6) than PDMS and PTMSP. Since the SBS matrix appears to primarily dictate the separation and barrier properties of the mixed-matrix (even at nanocellulose concentrations as high as 22 wt%),

Fig. 6. Plots demonstrating the permeability of ethanol and water as well as the membrane selectivity towards ethanol (dashed line at $\alpha = 1$ indicative of when the membrane changes from ethanol-to water-selective and vice-versa) of the nanocomposite SBS membranes as a function of (a) CNC and (b) OLA-CNC concentration in the nanocomposites (feed conditions: 10 wt% ethanol, 40 °C). Note that the y-axis scale of permeability for (a) CNC and (b) OLA-CNC containing SBS membranes is different. Measurements obtained with the cellulose-rich side of the membrane facing the feed. Reported values are the mean and standard deviation of $n = 2$ measurements.

it would be of interest to replace SBS with polymer matrices displaying superior ethanol-recovery properties (e.g., PDMS) and to investigate the potential of surface modified CNCs with oleic acid or other relatively non-polar moieties in mixed-matrix pervaporation designs for ethanol recovery. Considering also the renewable nature, tunable surface chemistry, and chemical stability of nanocellulose in many common solvents, biobased mixed-matrix pervaporation membranes featuring animal-, plant- or bacteria-derived polymers (e.g., natural rubber, chitosan, poly(butylene succinate)) and nanocellulose could be envisioned for the dehydration of organic solvents, the isolation of organics such as ethanol from water-based solutions, but also in organic-organic separations.

4. Conclusions

Pervaporation processes have attracted significant attention in the field of chemical engineering as an alternative option or complementary process to traditional unit operations such as distillation. In this work, we demonstrated that cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) present an excellent candidate for the preparation of mixed-matrix membranes with tunable properties by simply tailoring their surface chemistry. By using a simple esterification scheme, we successfully modified the surface of CNCs with oleic acid to downregulate the polarity and control the transversal distribution of nanocellulose as well as the pervaporation properties of the resulting nanocomposite membranes. CNCs — in their pristine or in a functionalized state — can be used as a simple means to adjust the polarity and regulate the permeation properties of the membranes. We also showed that this feature can be exploited in the context of achieving asymmetric transport properties by preparing compositionally-graded nanocomposites in the transversal direction (i.e., cross-sectional gradients). In principle, further improvement towards the recovery of ethanol or other valuable compounds with pervaporation could be achieved by decorating the surface of CNCs with fluorine- or silicon-based functionalities in order to downregulate the polarity of the CNCs and/or by employing a hydrophobic polymer matrix with excellent selectivity towards ethanol such as PDMS and PTMSP.

Author statement

A.K. and C.W. designed the research. A.K. and G.D. carried out the experiments. More specifically, A.K. prepared and characterized the membranes. G.D. synthesized the OLA-CNCs. All the authors interpreted the data. All authors contributed to writing the article, read, and approved the final manuscript.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2021.119473>.

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